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THE CHALLENGES OF GREEN FINANCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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ABSTRACT

Banks have a crucial role to play in financing the transition to a greener economy. Recognizing the importance of climate risks, banks undertake a series of activities to increase awareness of the consequences of climate change and define their role as a catalyst of financial flows towards green and sustainable projects.

The state of green loans approved to the private sector in 2023 in the Macedonian banking system has increased by 2.9 times compared to 2019, and their share in the total loans of banks at the end of 2023 is 4.5% and has a trend of increase.

The increase in climate risks driven by technological changes, government policies for climate neutrality until 2050, as well as changes in the inclinations of both investors and consumers, impose a need for proactive action by all actors in the ecosystem.

KEY WORDS: banks, green finance, green loans, climate changes

INTRODUCTION

The green economy represents a model of economic development that integrates the principles of sustainability, social inclusion and environmental protection. Transitioning to a green economy is a complex challenge, requiring large-scale transformations and investments in the economic and social landscape as a whole.

The transition to a green economy is necessary to limit the negative impact of climate change and has become one of the world's most urgent priorities. The Western Balkans is one of the regions in Europe most heavily affected by the impact of climate change.

Through the Green Agenda (European Commission, 2020), the Western Balkans will strive towards five targets aligning itself with the EU's green and digital transition (1) climate action, including decarbonisation, energy and mobility, (2) circular economy, addressing in particular waste, recycling, sustainable production and efficient use of resources, (3) biodiversity, aiming to protect and restore the natural wealth of the region, (4) fighting pollution of air, water and soil and (5) sustainable food systems and rural areas.

The Green Agenda offers significant opportunities for the business sector in the Western Balkans. By aligning with the Green Agenda businesses can position themselves at the forefront of the green transition and capitalise on various benefits.

For instance, it promotes investments in sustainable technologies and practices. This encouragement allows companies and investors to develop innovative solutions that contribute to the green transition while generating profits. The growing global focus and demand for green products and services providers will ensure that companies that truly innovate in this space will thrive.

Integration with the EU market means integrating with its industrial ecosystems as they transform in the spirit of the Green Deal of the EU. This implies not only the need for a green modernisation in enterprises, but also investments in the co-operative linkages in the industrial eco-systems such as innovation, inward foreign direct investment, export prerequisites and skills development. Their green focus can be informed by the smart specialisation strategy of the economies and regions.

At the same time, the green transition poses risks for firms, households and, consequently, financial institutions. The financial institutions would be exposed to the transition-related risks of households and nonfinancial corporations, mainly through their loan portfolios and securities holdings. Their risks would therefore be linked to the vulnerability of their counterparties in both the credit and the market-risk channels. Mapping firm-level changes in probabilities of default against information on banks'

individual corporate loans made it possible to assess the transmission of transition risk from firms to banks, the transmission of transition risk from households to banks being assessed on the basis of the projected deterioration in the credit quality of bank portfolios.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides a literature overview of the green financing and green economy. Section 3 describes the importance and definition of green loans and green bonds, Section 4 describes the situation with green loans in Macedonian banking system. Section 4 concludes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Vukovic, Korik, Lisjak (2019) the green economy is defined as an economy that is aimed at reducing risks to the environment, and aims at sustainable development without degrading the environment. The green economy cares about healthy ecosystems and sustainability, making a step towards a positive change in the way we live and work. It represents a holistic concept that encourages development but at the same time advocates respect and preservation of the regional and global ecosystem, improves human well-being and social equality, promoting sustainable economic development that will reduce environmental risks and challenges.

The green economy aims to reduce environmental risks and environmental deficiencies and strives for sustainable development without destroying the environment. The implementation of a green economy not only encourages companies to adopt environmental standards, but also opens doors to new market opportunities. In today's world, consumers are committed to environmentally friendly products and services, which means that companies that apply sustainable practices can create a clear competitive advantage in the market. Further efforts are therefore needed to develop a comprehensive approach to foster sustainable lifestyles and consumption, and to accompany consumers and public authorities towards sustainable choices.

The application of the policy to strengthen the environment in banks can stimulate their profitability in the long term (Rodrigues & Franco, 2023). Greater attention to the environment enables a higher quality of products and services in banks, as well as greater profitability in the long term. The authors, based on the analysis of the impact of green banking practices on the profitability of the Indonesian banking sector for the period from 2012 to

2016, confirmed that the daily operation of green banking, capital adequacy and liquidity positively affect the bank's profitability. Although a greater propensity for green lending is associated with lower profitability, it is necessary to strengthen the role of banks in strengthening environmental issues with public and government support. Their research found that components such as bank size, reputation, age, profitability, and investor responsiveness are driving elements for banks' green performance.

However, striking a balance between green initiatives and profitability can be challenging, especially in the short term. Banks need careful planning and adjustment of strategies in order to simultaneously meet sustainability requirements and achieve stable profitability. The long-term success of banks may depend on the ability to adapt their operations to changes in social and economic expectations, integrating sustainable practices that not only support the environment, but also contribute to their long-term business success.

The financial risks associated with climate change in recent years are analyzed by macroeconomic modeling and climate stress tests, which represent a tool for assessing the impact of assumed events on financial stability. The first ECB economy-wide climate stress test in 2021 showed that – all other things being equal – the earlier the transition happens, the smaller the financial risk, and consequently the less policy support is required to mitigate the costs. In fact, the short-term costs of a green transition would be more than offset by the long-term benefits (ECB, 2023). The increase in credit risk triggered by transition efforts over the first eight to ten years would be more than outweighed by the reduction in physical risks thereafter. The second economy-wide climate stress test, provided by ECB last year, follows up on the results of the first economy-wide stress test exercise. The best way to achieve a net-zero economy for firms, households and banks in the euro area is to accelerate the green transition to a rate that is faster than under current policies.

By comparing different transition scenarios, the results of the ECB economy-wide stress test show that acting immediately and decisively would provide significant benefits for the euro area economy and financial system, not only by maintaining the optimal net-zero emissions path (and therefore limiting the physical impact of climate change), but also by limiting financial risk. An accelerated transition to a carbon-neutral economy would be helpful to contain risks for financial institutions and would not generate financial stability concerns for the euro area, provided that firms and households could finance their green investments in an orderly manner. However, the heterogeneous

results across economic sectors and banks suggest that more careful monitoring of certain entities and subsets of credit exposures will be required during the transition process.

The current exercise found that large and systemically important institutions would experience a larger projected increase in transition-related credit risk than other banks under all three scenarios. Moreover, the credit risk increase for those banks most exposed to vulnerable firms would be non-linear, given that such firms account for a larger portfolio share.

The green transition would have a direct impact on households, with consequent spillovers to the financial sector. The household sector represents an equally important category of banks' counterparties. Indeed, loans to households and NFCs constitute around 40% and 37% of euro area banks' total loan exposures respectively. Transition risks affecting the household sector might therefore have quantitatively meaningful implications for the banking system, with heterogeneous effects across countries. Banks' credit risk would increase with transition risk and banks exposed to more vulnerable firms would be disproportionately more affected. The market risk channel acts through a repricing of banks' corporate bond portfolios based on sensitivity to transition risk over time.

After the publication of the first ECB climate stress test (Alogoskoufis et al., 2021), climate risk assessments by other jurisdictions have confirmed the importance of a timely transition to a net-zero economy and highlighted the risks stemming from inaction or a delayed response to climate change. Other exercises focusing on the impact of transition risks on Italian (Faeilla et al., 2022), Dutch (Caloia et al., 2022), French (Clerc et al., 2021), and Canadian (BoC, OSFI, 2022) financial institutions find effects for credit risks that are of a similar order of magnitude to this current exercise and more pronounced in energy-intensive sectors, such as the petroleum/oil sector.

GREEN FINANCING

In the framework of green financing, green loans play a key role. Loans are considered green if they are used for projects that significantly reduce the negative impact on the environment and mitigating the effects of climate change on the environment. It's a form of financing that enables borrowers to use the proceeds to exclusively fund projects that make a substantial contribution to an environmental objective.

According to World Bank (2021), a loan to be called a green loan should be structured in alignment to the Green Loan Principles which provide an international standard based on the following core components:

- *Use of Proceeds*: Designated Green Projects should provide clear environmental benefits, which will be assessed, measured, and reported by the borrower.
- *Process for Project Evaluation and Selection*: The borrower of a green loan should clearly communicate how it is organized to assess and select projects that will receive loan proceeds. In addition, the borrower explains how it will manage environmental and social risk of eligible projects.
- *Management of Proceeds*: The proceeds of a green loan should be credited to a dedicated account or tracked by the borrower to maintain transparency and promote the integrity of the product.
- *Reporting*: The principles recommend the use of qualitative performance indicators and, where feasible, quantitative performance measures (for example, energy capacity, electricity generation, greenhouse gas emissions reduced/avoided, etc.).

There are different types of green loans, including loans for energy efficiency, green building and waste management. Green loans not only provide financial resources, but also serve as a catalyst for creating public awareness and commitment in the fight against climate change and the preservation of natural resources.

Green loans play a key role in promoting sustainable development. They provide incentives for companies to adopt environmentally responsible practices and contribute to global efforts to combat climate change. This is not only beneficial for nature, but also for the lenders themselves, as long-term value is created by supporting environmentally sustainable projects.

One of the opportunity to fund projects that have positive environmental and/or climate benefits are green bonds. *Green bonds are popular* financial instruments for large institutional investors, for instance development banks, pension funds, insurance companies, government or non-financial corporates that seek to support green business purposes and support the global, green transition. At the end of 2023 year, the green bonds issuance in the world are in amount of 576 billion USD and record a rapid increase of 17.2 times compared by 2014 year. Analyzed dynamically, their increase since 2020 is especially present, while from a structural point of view, non-financial and

financial corporate have the largest share and increase, as well as Sovereign (Graph 1). The green bonds issuance in Europe are in amount of 304 billion USD and record increase of 13.8 times compared by 2014 year. They follow the same structure by type of issuer as bonds issued worldwide (Graph 2). Green banking services are related to financial activities and use various financial methods to promote environmental activities. The market risk channel acts through a repricing of banks' corporate bond portfolios based on sensitivity to transition risk over time.

Source: www.nbrm.mk

The challenges of applying green financing are more dimensional and structural. A robust and reliable system of measurement, reporting and verification of the impacts of green finance activities on the environment is needed. It requires a clear and consistent definition and classification of green finance activities and their eligibility criteria. This may involve trade-offs between environmental effectiveness and economic efficiency. A fair and transparent mechanism is needed to determine the prices of green loans and ensure their market liquidity.

A strong and efficient governance structure and regulatory framework is needed to ensure the credibility, integrity and accountability of the green credit system. The impact of banking regulation on green finance is significant. Regulatory measures and standards can have a direct and indirect effect on the development and supply of green loans. In many countries, the regulatory framework implements various mechanisms and incentives to strengthen the financing of sustainable projects and investments. That mean that banks could provide loans with less capital to finance projects that would reduce environmental risks in the long term. The Basel III regulatory standard requires banks to take into account the impact of specific environmental risks

when assessing banks' exposure to credit and operational risks. Certain regulatory institutions have already used measures within their competence to promote ecological sectors. For example, in Bangladesh is introduced a credit quota according to which at least 5% of commercial banks' bank loans should be directed to these sectors.

Another issue is standardization of relevant data. Financial regulators have to contribute to the development of databases, standardization of relevant data and methodologies that would enable a consistent and comparable way of analyzing the exposure of the financial sector to climate and environmental risks. Also, it is needed for integrating environmental and climate risks into risk assessment in the financial system.

GREEN FINANCING IN MACEDONIA

In recent years, the Republic of North Macedonia has been actively promoting the transition to a green economy, implementing a large number of measures and policies that support the sustainable use of natural resources and environmental protection. As part of the policies for the integration of the Republic of North Macedonia in the European Union are the provision of sustainable development and promotion of the green economy in the country. During the accession process, the country undertakes to harmonize the national legislation with the EU legislation in order to protect the environment, rational use of resources and energy efficiency in all sectors of the national economy and life. Of essential importance for the development of the country are the reforms in the field of environmental protection, sustainable development, as well as the issue of energy efficiency (Nedanovski & Danilovska, 2022).

The Macedonian banking system plays an important role in supporting green financing, providing favorable conditions for green loans and the development of specialized green products in cooperation with international organizations such as the EBRD and the World Bank. Green loans are becoming increasingly important in the context of national sustainable development efforts. Banks offer these loans as part of their strategy to support environmental initiatives, supporting projects that directly contribute to ecological balance and energy efficiency.

According to the data from the National Bank, green lending records a constant growth and at the end of 2023 green loans amount to 19.8 billion

denars. Compared to 2019, they have increased by 2.8 times (table number 1). Despite the constant growth dynamics, their participation in the credit portfolios of banks is still low and amounts to 4.4%.

Table 1. Bank green loans in Macedonia

in MKD 000.000

Year	Households	Share of green loans in total households' loans (in per cent)	Non-financial companies	Share of green loans in total non-financial companies' loans (in per cent)	Total	Share of green loans in total loans (in per cent)
2023	1.224	0,5	18.639	8,8	19.863	4,5
2022	1.309	0,6	14.081	6,9	15.390	3,6
2021	1.315	0,7	9.233	5,0	10.548	2,7
2020	1.432	0,8	7.434	4,4	8.866	2,5
2019	1.160	0,7	6.016	3,7	7.176	2,2

Green loans are granted both to the corporate sector and to the households, but predominantly with 93% participation are loans granted to non-financial legal entities. The total green loans to the non-financial sector recorded a growth of 3.1 times, and their participation in the total loans of this sector is 8.8%, recording an increase of 5.1 pp. Green loans are intended for projects that support sustainable, environmental goals, or goals that contribute to the green transition in society, such as developing new environmental technology.

Green loans to households have a minimum share of 0.5%, but banks are increasingly focusing on green loans for this sector.

The growth of green lending is mostly due to the loans taken by companies, while most green loans were given by large banks. At the end of 2023, the share of green loans approved by large banks is 66.7%, as opposed to small banks that participate with only 1.1% in total approved green loans in the banking sector (Graph 3). The share of green loans approved by medium-sized banks is 32.1% (Graph 4).

Source: www.nbrm.mk

The green bonds are issued at first time in 2023 year in the amount of 600 million EUR by Ministry of Finance. It's only 0,4% from the total bond issuance in the North Macedonia. The challenge and need is to increase green financing in the future by issuing bonds for that purpose.

The national strategies of the Republic of North Macedonia for small and medium-sized enterprises and sustainable development include measures to support the green economy by facilitating access to green loans and financial incentives for energy efficiency. The regulatory framework also plays a key role in encouraging green loans by providing tax breaks, subsidies and other financial incentives that make green investment more attractive. The National bank of the Republic of North Macedonia has adopted a climate risk strategy and guidelines for commercial banks on the manner of incorporating climate risks in their strategies and reports, with a preliminary analysis of banks' exposure to these risks. Also, The National Bank has included green financing as one of the key strategic goals in its medium-term strategic plan.

The green loans create competitive advantages for businesses that actively engage in sustainable practices, making them more attractive to investors and consumers who are increasingly looking for products and services with a low environmental impact. Some commercial banks in Macedonia have included adapting to new or changed products and services creating specific financial products to encourage energy efficiency and better environmental conditions.

Banks should regularly review and update their risk management systems, taking into account changes in the external environment as well as changes within the bank itself. The green loans often encourage innovation in bank operations, as they require the development of new financial products and approaches that support sustainable goals. The banking sector can see a long-term benefit in adapting its services to meet the growing demand for sustainable investments and environmental solutions.

The banks have the opportunity to become leaders in the development of sustainable practices, setting the financial sector industry on the path towards a green and sustainable financial model. With each project they support with green loans, banks not only advance their business models but also play a key role in building a sustainable and responsible society.

But, on that road they face more challenges. Companies, especially micro-enterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises, often do not have the necessary information and awareness to understand the climate and financial risks they face, nor knowledge about the usage and transparency of this type of data, thus reducing the ability of banks to effectively manage climate and environmental risks.

It needs to be strengthened the mechanisms for cooperation and support knowledge exchange among the companies, planning and finance and to build their capacity on areas such as natural capital accounting and valuation, green budgeting/green taxation and the use of market-based instruments, such as environmental taxes, charges and subsidies to steer markets. Strengthening capacities to monitor, promote and enforce compliance with environmental obligations is crucial. Education is key to positively affect behaviours regarding the environment, starting from an early age as well as to reskill workers from transition industries. The Green Agenda for our country needs to be reflected in the reforms of the education systems in order to guarantee that people are equipped and prepared for the labour market and society of tomorrow.

CONCLUSIONS

The basic principles of the green economy include environmental sustainability, social inclusion, efficient use of resources and economic fairness. It is necessary to create stimulating policies and regulations that support the transition to a green economy, that is, with a comprehensive

approach to social, environmental and economic challenges to create a long-term sustainable future based on sustainable practices.

Green loans enable reduction of energy costs, increase of competitiveness, access to new markets, and contribution to environmental protection. The future of green loans is linked to increasing awareness of environmental issues and the need for sustainable development. These loans will continue to play a key role in financing projects that improve the environmental conditions. Also, green loans open the door for banks to explore new market opportunities, such as green energy, renewable energy and sustainable infrastructure projects. This can increase banks' revenues and profits in the long run. Overall, green loans can have a positive effect on banks' profitability through portfolio diversification, opening new markets, improving reputation and trust, as well as receiving regulatory incentives. At the same time, an early start of the transition would allow banks to benefit from both lower credit risk and larger investment needs, thereby improving their income positions.

The National Bank of the Republic of North Macedonia took a proactive stance and set increased awareness of climate change and contribution to a green sustainable economy as one of its strategic goals. The Macedonian banks have a role as an accelerator of financial flows towards green and sustainable projects, along with strengthening the capacity for adequate management of climate risks. It is necessary to raise awareness of the importance of environmental protection and encourage responsible consumer behavior.

The private sector's role is also crucial. By investing in sustainable technologies and practices, companies and investors can signal and drive the green transition. They can leverage the Green Agenda's investment potential by innovating in green technologies and tapping into new markets for green products and services, reducing operational costs through energy efficiency improvements. This will then pave the way for new sustainable start-ups by reducing the barriers to entry.

In the future, the number of banks and financial institutions that will develop specialized green products is expected to increase as well as with introducing additional incentives and regulations to support these initiatives. The changes in the inclinations of both investors and consumers, impose a need for proactive action by all actors in the ecosystem.

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